

सत्यं शिवं सुन्दरम्
Estd. 1949

Journal of
The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda

Certificate of Publication

Certificate of publication for the article titled:

POTENTIAL OF NANOPARTICLES IN REFRIGERATION SYSTEM WITH NATURAL
REFRIGERANT - A REVIEW

Authored by

Kumbhar Anil Hiralal

ज्ञान-विज्ञान विमुक्तये

UGC

Volume No .58 No.1(I) 2024

Approved in

Journal of The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda

ISSN : 0025-0422

(UGC CARE Group I Journal)

Journal MSU of Baroda